

МОРАЛЬНАЯ И СПЕЦИАЛЬНАЯ ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКАЯ
ПОДГОТОВКА БОРЦА

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Аннотация: В этой статье Спортивная деятельность борца, протекающая на фоне высокого нервнопсихического напряжения и воздействия на организм часто неблагоприятных факторов внешней среды, предъявляет высокие требования к его моральным и психическим качествам и возможностям. В этих условиях особую актуальность приобретает оценка функционального состояния и эффективности тренировки, а также прогнозирование его работоспособности.

Ключевые слова: Физической подготовленности, скоростно-силовых качеств, технико-тактических навыков, взрывной силой, гибкость, специальной выносливостью, ловкость и сила.

MORAL AND SPECIAL PSYCHOLOGICAL TRAINING OF A WRESTLER

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Annotation: In this article, the sports activity of a wrestler, proceeding against the background of high neuropsychic stress and the impact on the body of often unfavorable environmental factors, places high demands on his moral and mental qualities and capabilities. In these conditions, the assessment of the functional state and effectiveness of training, as well as the prediction of its working ability, becomes particularly relevant.

Keywords: Physical fitness, speed and strength qualities, technical and tactical skills, explosive strength, flexibility, special endurance, agility and strength.

In the sport of the highest achievements, physical and mental stress reach their limits. The responsibility that falls on the athlete sometimes weighs heavily on the psyche of the wrestler, demanding from him the maximum manifestation of all qualities. Although, in principle, the mental training of an athlete cannot be

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separated from his training as a whole, nevertheless, this issue should be constantly kept in view. The basis for the formation of all positive mental qualities is the motivation to achieve the highest sports result.

We know that motivation is a special state of an athlete's personality, which is formed on the basis of the correlation of his leading needs with the subject of sports activity. In case of coincidence of these principles of activity, there is a steady desire to master the subject of sports activity, which serves as the basis for setting goals aimed at achieving the highest sports results.

When a wrestler is adequately motivated, then it is possible to develop the mental qualities he needs. At the same time, it is necessary to remember: mental preparation is not just conversations and the suggestion of certain truths to an athlete. This is primarily a purposeful work to improve his technical and tactical skills on the basis of comprehensive physical fitness. Let's say a wrestler needs to develop courage. First of all, it is necessary to understand why he has cowardice. Which of the opponents he is afraid of and why. If you look deeper into this issue, you can find out that the nature of cowardice lies in the fact that the wrestler does not know how to defend himself well from the opponent's radical reception or is inferior in physical strength, endurance or speed, etc. It means that the work on the formation of courage should be primarily related to the elimination of existing gaps in one or the other another section of the skill. At the same time, it is important that the wrestler, even before meeting with the main competitor, make sure that these gaps are eliminated. Thus, it is necessary to work on other mental qualities, but, by the way, in the presence of high motivation, the need for this may not arise, since motivation is a very strong incentive in the formation of the mental qualities necessary for victory.

A coach plays a special role in the formation of motivation for sports activities. There are quite a few works in the scientific and methodological literature on sports devoted to the role of a coach in the formation of an athlete's personality. However, their pedagogical significance increases dramatically if you look at the coach as the main person in the formation of motivation to achieve the highest sports result. A coach's personal positive example is not only a role model for developing socially useful qualities, character traits, and behavioral skills.

The formation of motivation is of great importance for families and schools. Unfortunately, in the pedagogical literature devoted to the role of family and school in the formation of a child's personality, little attention is paid to the tonic function of these social groups. Meanwhile, the role of parents, teachers, and other organizers in the formation of certain motivational attitudes is also very great, the

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sports team plays a big role in the formation of motivation. His motivation largely depends on the microclimate in the team where the wrestler trains. In some cases, it may increase, in others it may weaken. Coaches have repeatedly faced the fact that an athlete who joined their team suddenly lost those qualities for which he was invited from another club. Most often, the reason is explained by the fact that the athlete did not fit the technical and tactical features of his skill, according to mental qualities

In the formation of special mental qualities in wrestlers of the highest qualification, conversations, exercises, fights of a special orientation, competitions for the purpose of solving specific tasks are the main means. Sports competition, as a rule, causes athletes strong emotional experiences. There is an opinion that excessive excitement, especially long before the competition, has a negative impact on the athlete's activity. In the psychology of sports, a whole complex of factors is called as the causes leading to a violation of emotional stability: from the peculiarities of the nervous system, temperament and other mental qualities to such personality characteristics as motivation, level of claims, style of behavior, knowledge and skill, and much more (L.D. Hessen, 1977, V.M. Pisarenko 1980, B. A. Vetkin 1987 and others)

Of course, the competition has a strong impact on the mental, and through it on the physical condition of the athlete, and this cannot but affect his motivation. About the degree and nature of this influence, we judge the degree of interest of the athlete in the presence of negative psychogenic effects. As indicators of dynamic research, athletes are most often exposed to negative psychogenic effects during competitions at the age of over 20 years. This is probably due to the theft of the level of competitions and the significance of winning them. At the same time, studies have shown that high performance is inherent, as a rule, in athletes who perform less successfully in competitions. This fact should be considered as a direct proof that during the competition, athletes are under stress not only strongly motivated, but only having a certain motivation structure.

The history of sports is replete with a huge number of examples of when an athlete shows good results in training, but at competitions he seems to be replaced. Very often, the same phenomenon is detected if an athlete is called to another city, republic. How many labels were distributed incriminating mental instability, uncontrollability, and a couple of cowardice. This is a serious problem and requires its own special solution. However, it will be very difficult to do this if you do not see a direct connection with the problems of motives here.

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We believe it is necessary to emphasize that changes in the mental state of an athlete have a specific "material" basis. Uncertainty, fear, lack of will, the birth of mistakes made in the preparation of the athlete. As a result of methodological errors, an athlete develops inadequate motivation and, as a result, his emotional stability is violated. Conversely, the training process, built taking into account the individual characteristics of the wrestler, allows you to reinforce the motivation to achieve the highest results, and this, in turn, leads to the development of the wrestler's determination and confidence in victory.

In relation to self-regulation of the emotional state, we can only say the following. A wrestler needs to learn how to choose effective ways to distract himself from thoughts about competitions. Ways to fall asleep on the eve of competitions. Here it is best not just to get away from these thoughts, but to consciously weigh everything and figure it out to the end. In other words, remove uncertainty.

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